

YOPIQ BOSH MIYA JAROHLAR BILAN KASALLANGAN BEMORLARDA IKKILAMCHI NEYROPROTEKSIYANING PATOGENETIK TAMOYILLARI.

(Sharh maqolasi)

Ibragimov N.K., Kenjaev L.T.

Toshkent Tibbiyot Akademiyasi Anesteziologiya va Reanimatologiya kafedrası.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15011072>

Annotatsiya: yopiq bosh miya jarohati butun dunyo bo'ylab o'lim va og'ir nogironlikning asosiy sababidir. Qurbonlarini davolash va reabilitatsiya qilish turli mamlakatlar byudjetlariga katta ziyon yetkazadi. Psixologik va jismoniy yuk, hayot sifatining pasayishi va sezilarli xarajatlar faqat ushbu bemorlarni boshqarishning qo'shimcha, yanada murakkab va samarali variantlari zarurligini ta'kidlashi mumkin. Neyroproteksiya kontseptsiyasi ishemiya tomonidan qo'zg'atilgan murakkab patofiziologik o'zgarishlardan foydalangan holda yaxshiroq natijaga erishish vositasi bo'lib, ko'plab terapevtik va jarrohlik strategiyalarining markazida bo'lib kelgan va shunday bo'lib qoladi. Eksitotoksiklik, apoptoz va oksidlovchi stressdan yallig'lanishgacha bo'lgan YBMJning turli mexanizmlarini keltirib chiqaradigan bir necha turdagi asoratlar o'rganildi va ularning aksariyati klinik bosqichda umidsizlikka olib keldi va zararining har bir bosqichida zararining u yoki bu yo'lini oldini olish yoki oqibatlarini minimallashtirish uchun himoya - neyroproteksiya qilish kerak. Bu esa neyroproteksiyaning muhim davolash taktikasi bo'lib qolayotganini ko'rsatadi. Ushbu sharhda klinik jihatdan o'rganilgan neyroproteksiya usullari, ularning mexanizmlari, natijalari neyroproteksiyaning potentsial maqsadlari va maqsadli davolash usullari haqida qisqacha ma'lumot berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: neyroproteksiya, yopiq bosh miya jarohati, apoptoz, yallig'lanish, eksitotoksiklik, oksidlovchi stress, kallidinogenaza.

ПАТОГЕНЕТИЧЕСКИЕ ОСНОВЫ ВТОРИЧНОЙ НЕЙРОПРОТЕКЦИИ У БОЛЬНЫХ С ЗАКРЫТЫМИ ЧЕРЕПНО-МОЗГОВЫМИ ТРАВМАМИ.

(Комментарий к статье)

Аннотация: Закрытая черепно-мозговая травма является основной причиной смерти и тяжелой инвалидности во всем мире. Лечение и реабилитация жертв ложатся огромным бременем на бюджеты разных стран. Психологическая и физическая нагрузка, снижение качества жизни и значительные расходы могут только подчеркнуть необходимость дополнительных, более сложных и эффективных вариантов лечения этих пациентов. Концепция нейропротекции как средства достижения лучших результатов путем использования сложных патофизиологических изменений, вызванных ишемией, была и остается основой многих терапевтических и хирургических стратегий. Изучено несколько типов осложнений, вызывающих различные механизмы НМЗП, от эксайтотоксичности, апоптоза и окислительного стресса до воспаления, и большинство из них привели к разочарованию на клинической стадии, а на каждой стадии повреждения необходима защита — нейропротекция — для предотвращения того или иного пути повреждения или минимизации последствий. Это свидетельствует о том, что нейропротекция остается важной тактикой лечения. В этом обзоре представлен краткий обзор клинически изученных методов нейропротекции, их механизмов, результатов, потенциальных целей нейропротекции и таргетной терапии.

Ключевые слова: нейропротекция, закрытая черепно-мозговая травма, апоптоз, воспаление, эксайтотоксичность, окислительный стресс, каллидиногеназа.

PATHOGENETIC PRINCIPLES OF SECONDARY NEUROPROTECTION IN PATIENTS WITH CLOSED HEAD INJURIES.

(Review article)

Abstract: closed head injuries are the leading cause of death and severe disability worldwide. Treatment and rehabilitation of their victims cause significant damage to the budgets of different countries. Psychological and physical burden, reduced quality of life and significant costs can only emphasize the need for additional, more complex and effective options for managing these patients. The concept of neuroprotection, as a means of achieving better outcomes by exploiting the complex pathophysiological changes induced by ischemia, has been and remains at the heart of many therapeutic and surgical strategies. Several types of complications have been studied, which cause different mechanisms of TBI, from excitotoxicity, apoptosis and oxidative stress to inflammation, and most of them have led to clinical disappointment, and at each stage of damage, protection - neuroprotection - is necessary to prevent one or another path of damage or minimize the consequences. This indicates that neuroprotection remains an important treatment tactic. This review provides a brief overview of clinically studied neuroprotection methods, their mechanisms, results, potential targets of neuroprotection and targeted therapies.

Keywords: neuroprotection, closed brain injury, apoptosis, inflammation, excitotoxicity, oxidative stress, kallidinogenase.

KIRISH

Yopiq bosh miya jarohati (YBMJ) butun dunyo bo'ylab o'lim va og'ir nogironlikning asosiy sababidir. YBMJ qurbonlarini davolash va rehabilitatsiya qilish turli mamlakatlar byudjetlariga katta zarar olib keladi [1, 5]. Miya shikastlanishi intensiv terapiya taktikasida miya shishi doimo mutaxassislarining diqqat markazida bo'lib kelgan. Shikastlanish natijasida jarohat hududlarida ba'zi hujayralarni mexanik ravishda yo'q qilish kuzatiladi. Xuddi shu narsa, ammo diffuz tarzda, penumbra sezilarli gipoksiya va arterial gipotenziya bilan sodir bo'ladi. Hujayralarning bir qismi nobud bo'lganda ("shikastlangan neyronlar hovuzi"), kaltsiy, kaliy va biologik faol moddalarning yuqori konsentratsiyasi bo'lgan giperosmolyar suyuqlik hujayra ichi va hujayralararo bo'shliqqa kirib, membranalarning shikastlanishiga va qo'shni hujayralarning o'limiga olib keladi, ularning hujayra ichidagi tarkibi "shafqatsiz doira" tamoyiliga muvofiq sitotoksik ta'sir ko'rsatadi [3, 4, 6].

Miya ishemiyasi - qon ta'minoti buzilishi tufayli miya hujayralarining to'satdan nobud bo'lishi. Bu energiya almashinuvining buzilishi, membrana depolarizatsiyasi, oqsil sintezining ingibitsiyasi, Ca²⁺ oqimi, glutamatning haddan tashqari stimulyatsiyasidan chiqarilishi, sitoskeletal va membrananing shikastlanishi, mikroglial faollashtirilgan yallig'lanish va hujayra membranalarning lizosomal o'limi bilan boshlanadigan halokatli patofiziologik hodisalar kaskadi bo'lib xizmat qiladi. Ushbu hodisalar birlashganda, sinergik tarzda harakat qiladi va ular o'z-o'zidan ko'ra kuchliroq ta'sir ko'rsatadi [4-7]. BMJ tarqalishi ko'pincha mehnatga layoqatli yoshdagi aholida kuzatilgan bo'lsada, hozirda tasdiqlangan yagona davolash to'qima plazminogen faollashtiruvchisi bo'lib, u o'zining cheklovlari tufayli (kichik vaqt oralig'i va qon ketish xavfi) ko'p bemorlar uchun har doim ham mos kelmaydi [8-10]. Miya shikastlanishini davolashning yangi yondashuvlari keng qamrovli o'rganildi va ularning ba'zilari shikastlanish natijasida kelib chiqqan yoki undan keyin bir necha soniya yoki daqiqalar ichida sodir bo'lgan patofiziologik o'zgarishlarga bevosita murojaat qiladi.

ASOSIY QISM

Neyroproteksiya 1980-yildan beri o'rganilib kelinmoqda, birinchi klinik sinovlar o'tkazilgan va bu turli darajadagi muvaffaqiyatlarga erishgan [11, 12]. Neyroproteksiya odatda hujayra ichidagi kaltsiyning ko'payishini ingibitsiya qilish yoki erkin radikal reaksiyalarining faollashishini va hujayra o'limini bostirish orqali miya to'qimalarining infarkti hajmini cheklash yoki kamaytirishga hamda atrofdagi zaif hujayralarni saqlashga qaratilgan jarayon sifatida ta'riflanadi [13]. Yakuniy maqsad neyronlarning yo'qolishini to'xtatish yoki hech bo'lmaganda sekinlashtirish orqali kasallikning rivojlanishini va ikkilamchi zararni oldini olish yoki sekinlashtirishdir. Neyroprotektiv terapiyaning asosiy maqsadlari oksidlovchi stress, mitoxondrial disfunktsiya, apoptoz, autofagiya, eksitotoksiklik va yallig'lanish o'zgarishlarini bartaraf etishdir [8]. Ba'zan ishemik deb ataladigan bu patofiziologik o'zgarishlar miya yarim ishemiyasi sindromining natijasidir va ko'pchilik ishemik neyronlarning o'limiga sabab bo'ladigan kaskad [14]. Yuqoridagi o'zgarishlarga to'g'ridan-to'g'ri yoki bilvosita ta'sir ko'rsatadigan bir nechta potentsial farmakologik vositalar ularning neyroprotektiv salohiyati uchun o'rganilgan va kelajakda antiishemik vositalar sifatida foydalanish umidida bir nechta klinik sinovlardan o'tgan. Ushbu sharhning maqsadi neyroproteksiya qiziqishning patofiziologik mexanizmlarini o'rganish va natijalardan qat'iy nazar, klinik sinovdan o'tgan neyroprotektiv muolajalar haqida umumiy ma'lumot berishdir.

Neyroproteksiya qaratilgan ishemiyaning patofiziologik mexanizmlari

1.1 Eksitotoksiklik - bu glutamat kabi ko'p miqdorda toksik neyrotransmitterlarning hujayradan tashqari bo'shliqqa chiqishi tufayli asab hujayralarining haddan tashqari qo'zg'alishi bilan tavsiflangan jarayon bo'lib, natijada hujayra o'limiga ya'ni apoptozni jadallashtiradi [15-18]. Glutamatning giperproduksiyasi glutamat ionotrop retseptorlari - N-metil D-aspartat (NMDA) retseptorlari, a-amino-3-gidroksi-5-metil-4-izoksazolpropion kislota (AMPA) retseptorlarini qo'zg'atib, Ca⁺ning hujayra ichiga siljishiga va depolarizatsiyasiga olib keladi [19-21]. Hujayra ichidagi Ca⁺ning yuqori darajasi asab hujayralariga toksik ta'sir qiladi. Ko'p miqdordagi kaltsiy fosfolipazlar, proteazlar va kalpain kabi bir qancha fermentlarning faollashtiruvchisi bo'lib, hujayra tuzilishiga va dezoksiribonuklein kislotasiga (DNK) halokatli ta'sir ko'rsatadi [22]. Sitozolda kaltsiy yuqori darajasi bilvosita yana bir tezkor ta'sirini ya'ni mitoxondrial o'tish membranalarining blokirovkasi bo'lib, ular bo'shliq vazifasini bajaradi, shu bilan o'tkazuvchanlikni oshiradi, shish paydo bo'lishiga va reaktiv kislorod turlarining chiqishiga olib keladi [21]. Bundan tashqari, bularning barchasi adenozin trifosfat (ATF) ishlab chiqarilishiga ta'sir qiladi [24], bu ion gradientlarining yo'qolishiga va glutamatning so'rilishini to'xtatilishiga va keyinchalik to'planishi tufayli glutamat retseptorlarining faollashuvining buzilishiga olib keladi [24]. Shunday qilib, glutamatning eksitotoksikligi miya ishemiyasi sindromi patologiyasining muhim jihati va uning nekroz, apoptoz va autofagiya boshlanishi uchun asosdir. Eksitotoksiklik jarayoniga to'g'ridan-to'g'ri ta'sir qilish orqali natijani yaxshilash maqsadida bir nechta usullar tekshirildi. Umumiy g'oya glutamat chiqarilishini ingibitsiya qilish yoki miyadagi glutamat retseptorlari ta'sirini blokirovka qilishdir. Turli xil dori-darmonlar qoniqarsiz natijalar bilan klinik sinovlardan o'tkazildi.

1.2 Kaltsiy kanal blokatori. Ushbu kichik guruhga nimodipin kabi dorilar kiradi, dastlab gipertenziyani davolash uchun ishlab chiqilgan digidropiridinli kaltsiy kanallari blokatori. Hozirgi vaqtda u asosan miyadagi vazospazmini va unga bog'liq ishemiyani oldini olish uchun ishlatiladi. Shuningdek, Ca⁺ kanallarni bloklash orqali ishemik hududda qisqaruvchanlikni kamaytiradi va O₂ga bo'lgan ehtiyojni kamaytiradi. U kuchlanishga bog'liq kaltsiy kanallariga ta'siri tufayli

neyroprotektor sifatida taklif qilingan. Dastlab istiqbolli bo'lsada, uning TBI bemorlariga ta'sirini baholagan 28 ga yaqin sinovlar nazorat guruhiga nisbatan nimodipin bilan davolangan bemorlarda o'lim darajasida farq yo'qligini aniq ko'rsatdi [25].

1.3 NMDA antagonistlari. Asosan NMDA retseptorlari (NMDAR) ta'siriga ingibitiv yoki antagonist qiluvchi ta'sir ko'rsatadigan anestetiklardan tashkil topgan NMDA antagonistlari NMDAR ionotropiyasi tufayli eksitotoksiklikni davolash uchun tekshirilgan. Ular ikkita toifaga bo'linadi: raqobatbardosh (glutamatni bog'lash joyini blokirovka qilish) va raqobatdosh bo'lmagan (NMDARni allosterik bog'lash orqali ingibitsiya qilish) antagonistlari bizning e'tiborimiz mavzusidir. NMDA antagonistlari orasida magniy, raqobatdosh bo'lmagan antagonist va kuchlanish bilan bog'langan kaltsiy kanallarining blokeridir [26]. Magniy potensial antiexsitotoksik vosita sifatida o'rganilgan va ayniqsa kalamush insult modelida o'rta miya arteriyasi (O'MA) oklyuziyasidan so'ng darhol qo'llanilganda umid beruvchi natijalarni ko'rsatdi [27]. Magniyning samaradorligini baholash bo'yicha ikkita yirik (intravenoz magniy insult tadqiqoti) tadqiqot o'tkazildi.

YBMJ boshlanganidan keyin 12 soat ichida yuqori dozali magniyning ko'p markazli randomizatsiyalangan nazorat ostida sinovi [28] va ko'p markazli, randomizatsiyalangan, ikki marta platsebo-nazorat ostidagi tadqiqot [29], unda III-bosqich tadqiqoti boshlanganidan keyin 2 soat ichida magniy boshqariladi [30]. Afsuski, ikkala tadqiqot ham nazorat guruhi bilan solishtirganda, o'lim yoki nogironlik bo'ladimi, natijalarda sezilarli yaxshilanishni ko'rsata olmadi [28, 30]. Yana bir raqobatbardosh antagonist Selfotel eksperimental tadqiqotlarda O'MA oklyuziyasidan keyin 5 minut ichida yuborilganda infarkt hajmini sezilarli darajada kamaytirishi ko'rsatilgan [31-33]. U odamlarda o'zining samaradorligi va xavfsizligini II-bosqich tadqiqotida va 90-kundagi Barthel indeksini mustaqil baholash orqali baholangan natijalarning sezilarli yaxshilanishini nazorat qilish bilan solishtirganda isbotladi [34]. Biroq, insult boshlanganidan keyin 6 soat ichida 567 bemorni o'z ichiga olgan ikkita ko'rko'rona, randomizatsiyalangan, platsebo-nazoratli, parallel dizayndagi ikkita sinov 3-bosqichi sinovlari yuqori o'lim darajasi va asosiy natijaga terapevtik ta'sir ko'rsatmasligi sababli to'xtatildi [35].

1.4 AMPA antagonistlari. Raqobatbardosh AMPA retseptorlari (AMPA) antagonisti YM872, zonampanel nomi bilan tanilgan, kinoksalindionga asoslangan dori, uning neyroprotektiv xususiyatlari uchun ham tekshirilgan [36]. YM872 infarkt hajmini kamaytirishi va kalamush embolik insult modelida simptomlarni yaxshilashi mumkinligi ko'rsatilgan [37]. Ushbu mexanizm kortikal to'qimalarning yo'qolishi va miya shishishining kamayishi bilan bog'liq deb ishoniladi [38]. Biroq, gallyutsinatsiyalar, katatoniya va qo'zg'atuvchanlik kabi jiddiy nojo'ya ta'sirlar tufayli klinik sinovlar erta tugatildi [39].

2. Apoptoz. Uzoq vaqt davomida YBMJdan keyin hujayra o'limi faqat plazma membranasining buzilishi va hujayra ichidagi tarkibning chiqishi bilan yakunlangan zarar yetkazuvchi hodisalar bilan tavsiflangan nekrozning natijasi deb hisoblangan [40]. Bu hodisa ishemik penumbra sodir bo'ladi [41]. Biroq, qo'shimcha dalillar shuni ko'rsatdiki, apoptoz-dasturlashtirilgan hujayra o'limining bir shakli, hayvonlar modellarida ishemik miya shikastlanishidan keyin muhim rol o'ynaydi [42, 43]. Bu hodisa asosan apoptotik kaskadlar bilan belgilanadi va ular ko'plab o'zgarishlarni o'z ichiga oladi. Jumladan: hujayra ichidagi Ca⁺ning ko'payishi, mitoxondrial disfunktsiyani rag'batlantiradigan va antiapoptotik jarayonni to'xtatadigan prostata apoptozi javobi 4 kabi oqsillarning ko'payishi, mitoxondrial membrananing depolarizatsiyasi, yakuniy natija sifatida kaspazalarning sitoxrom C faollashuvi va yadro DNKning chiqarilishi [44]. So'nggi paytlarda apoptoz ta'siriga qarshi turish orqali

neyroproteksiyaga erishish maqsadi ko'pchilikning e'tiborini tortdi [45]. Bir nechta antiapoptotik birikmalar eksperimental modellarda muvaffaqiyatli sinovdan o'tkazildi, ular zarar maydonini sezilarli darajada qisqartirish, kaspazani ingibitsiya qilish, proapoptotik gen ekspressiyasini blokirovka qilish va antiapoptotik gen ekspressiyasini rag'batlantirish. Biroq, eksperimental natijalar har doim ham klinik natijalarga to'g'ri kelavermaydi. Klinik jihatdan baholangan formulalar orasida eritropoetin (EPO) va serebrolizin YBMJni davolashda foydalanish mumkinligi uchun sinovdan o'tkazildi.

2.1 Eritropoetin (EPO). Eritropoetinni rag'batlantirish orqali qizil qon hujayralarini ishlab chiqarish funksiyasidan tashqari, qarama-qarshi tadqiqotlar EPO bir qator harakatlarga ega ekanligini ko'rsatdi, shu jumladan angiogenezni rag'batlantirish, EPO retseptorlarini faollashtirish orqali hujayra omon qolishini rag'batlantirish, buning natijasida to'qimalarga antiapoptotik ta'sir ko'rsatadi [46, 47]. Rekombinant inson eritropoetini (rhEPO) bilan oldindan inkubatsiya qilingan kortikal hujayralarda ko'rsatilgan XIAP va c-IAP2 apoptoz ingibitori genlarining ko'payishi orqali apoptotik va antiapoptotik gen ekspressiyasiga ta'sir qiladi deb ishoniladi [48]. Bundan tashqari, rhEPOdan so'ng, gipokampusning CA1 ishemik hududida B-hujayrali limfoma extralarini (bcl-xL) ko'payishi ko'rsatilgan [49]. Pilot tadqiqotida BMJ bilan og'riyaning bemorlari EPO ning xavfsizligi va foydasini ko'rsatgan bo'lsada, bu natijalar kengroq tadqiqotda tasdiqlanmagan [50, 51]. Bundan tashqari, YBMJ boshlanganidan keyin 9 soat ichida granulotsit-koloniyani stimulyatsiya qiluvchi omil (G-CSF) yoki platsebo olgan miya ishemiyasi sindromi bo'lgan 328 bemorda o'tkazilgan kengroq tadqiqot (AXIS-2) 90-kuni birlamchi yakuniy nuqta yoki klinik natijada hech qanday farqni aniqlamadi [9].

2.2 Serebrolizin. Serebrolizin - past molekulyar og'irlikdagi neuropeptidlarning tozalangan peptidlari va cho'chqa miyasidan olingan erkin aminokislotalarning aralashmasi, shu jumladan: (lekin ular bilan cheklanmasdan) miyadan olingan neyrotrofik omil, glial hujayradan olingan neyrotrofik omil, asab o'sish omili [52, 53]. Erkin radikal hosil bo'lishini, mikroglial faollashuvni, neyroyallig'lanishni, kalpain faolligini/apoptozni bostirish orqali neyroprotektiv xususiyatlar va eksitotoksiklikga qarshi samaradorlikni ko'rsatdi, shuningdek, neyrotrofik faollikni namoyish etdi [54-57]. Oldingi tadqiqotlar serebrolizinning funksional natijani sezilarli darajada yaxshilashi degan xulosaga keldi, ammo infarkt hajmini kamaytirmadi [58]. Bu neyroblastlarning ko'payishi, ko'chishi va omon qolishi bilan bog'liq deb ishoniladi [59]. Bundan tashqari, ushbu tadqiqotlardan birida 30, 60 va 90-kunlarda o'ng o'rta miya arteriyasining pulsatsiyalanish indeksining (PI) pasayishi kuzatildi [60]. Ushbu ma'lumotlarning barchasi miya ishemiyasi sindromida Serebrolizinning klinik qo'llanilishini ko'rsatadi, ammo qo'shimcha tadqiqotlar talab etiladi.

3. Yallig'lanish. Markaziy asab tizimining yallig'lanishi haqidagi birinchi xabarlar 1900-yillarga to'g'ri keladi va keyingi kashfiyotlar neyrogenezni modulyatsiya qilishda yallig'lanish vositachilariga ta'sir qiladi. Miya shikastlanishining har qanday shakli, u gipoksiya, ishemiya yoki infeksiya bo'lsin, jiddiy oqibatlariga olib keladi va xarakterli yallig'lanish reaksiyalarini keltirib chiqaradi. Miya yallig'lanishi BMJdan keyin shikastlanishning ikkilamchi mexanizmi sifatida qaraladi va reaktiv kislorod turlari yoki nekrotik hujayralar kabi bir qancha omillarning natijasidir [61, 62]. Asosiy ishtirokchilar va vositachilar mikroglia, astrositlar va periferik makrofaqtlardir. Bu omillar mikroglia faollashishiga olib keladi, bu esa sitokin ishlab chiqarishni ko'paytirishga va miya qon tomirlarida adgezion molekularining induksiyasiga olib keladi [63, 64]. Adgezion molekulari o'z navbatida, aylanib yuruvchi leykotsitlarning yopishishini keltirib chiqaradi, bu esa mikrotomirlarning tiqilib qolishiga va miya parenximasiga immun

hujayralarining infiltratsiyasiga olib keladi. Faollashgan yallig'lanish hujayralari ikki tomonlama ta'sirga ega bo'lgan bir qator yallig'lanishga qarshi va yallig'lanishga qarshi sitokinlar va kimyokinlar kabi turli xil sitotoksik molekulalarni ishlab chiqaradi. Bir tomondan, u miyaning immun himoyasini ta'minlaydi, boshqa tomondan, u qon-miya to'sig'ini buzilishiga va neyronlarning o'limiga olib keladigan yallig'lanishning regenerativ halqasini qo'zg'atadi [65, 66]. Yillar davomida va muvaffaqiyatli eksperimental tadqiqotlardan so'ng, ma'lum yallig'lanishga qarshi strategiyalarning qiymatini baholash uchun bir nechta klinik sinovlar o'tkazildi. Ushbu sinovlarning ba'zilar kutilmagan yon ta'sirlar yoki samarasizligi tufayli muvaffaqiyatsizlikka uchragan bo'lsada, bir nechtasi hali ham neyroyallig'lanishga ijobiy tasir qiladi deb ishontirmoqda.

3.1 Kranioserebral gipotermiya (KSG). KSG ishemiya yoki BMJdan keyin davr tana haroratini ma'lum vaqt davomida boshqarish orqali natijalarni yaxshilashga qaratilgan [67]. Gipotermiya metabolizmni sekinlashtirib, miyaning kislorodga bo'lgan talabini kamaytirish orqali neyroprotektiv vosita sifatida ishlaydi [68-71]. Bir qancha keyingi tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatdiki, gipotermiya metabolik yo'llarga ushbu chegaralardan tashqari ta'sir qiladi. Aniqlanishicha, gipotermiyaning neyroprotektiv ta'siri ostida yotgan mexanizmlar quyidagilardan iborat: miya metabolizmi, mitoxondriyal shikastlanish va disfunktsiya, reperfuziya shikastlanishi, ion pompasi disfunktsiyasi va hujayra ichiga kaltsiy oqimi, neyroeksitotoksiklikni bloklash, sitotoksik shish paydo bo'lishi, hujayra ichidagi atsidoz, erkin radikal ishlab chiqarish, apoptoz, kalpain-proteolizi, DNK shikastlanishi, tomir o'tkazuvchanligi, qon-miya to'sig'ining o'tkazuvchanligi, qon ivishining faollashuvi, mikrotrombning shakllanishi va immunitetning oshishi [72].

Biroq, gipotermiyaning neyroprotektiv ta'sirini tushuntirish uchun bitta omildan foydalanish juda qiyin, chunki gipotermiya ishemik kaskadning eksitotoksiklik, apoptoz, yallig'lanish, erkin radikal ishlab chiqarish, qon oqimi va intrakranial bosimgacha bo'lgan ko'plab yo'llariga ta'sir qiladi [73, 74]. Immunologik nuqtai nazardan, gipotermiyaning asosiy ta'siri nafaqat mikroglialning faollashishi va ishemik hududlarda neyrotrofillar sonining kamaytiradi [75]. Shuningdek, reaktiv kislorod turlari (ROS) [76], adgezion molekulalari, makrofag yallig'lanish oqsili-3 a, yallig'lanish oldi sitokinlar, o'simta nekrozi omili alfa (TNF-a), interleykin 6 (IL-6), interleykin 1 (IL-1) va reaktivlar sonini faollashtirilgan B hujayralarining kappa yengil zanjirini kuchaytiruvchi omil (NF-kB) kamaytiradi. Bundan tashqari, u yallig'lanishda muhim ferment tizimi bo'lgan mitogen bilan faollashtirilgan protein kinazaga ta'sir qilishi ko'rsatilgan [78]. Birgalikda bu dalillar TBIdan keyingi terapiyada maqsadli haroratni boshqarish muhim rol o'ynashini ko'rsatadi.

3.2 Minosiklin. Minosiklin - keng spektrli bakteriostatik antibiotik, tetratsiklinlar oilasiga mansub yallig'lanishga qarshi, antiapoptoz, gemato-enseffalik barierni (GEB) himoya qilish, mikroglial faollashuvni kamaytirish, matritsa metalloproteinaza (MMP)-9ni kamaytirishdan azot oksidi (NO) hosil bo'lishigacha bo'lgan bir qancha neyroprotektiv xususiyatlarga ega. [79-82]. Minosiklinning yallig'lanishga qarshi funktsiyalari kaspaza-3, kaspaza-1, siklooksigenaza-2, induksiyalangan azot oksidi sintaza, p38 mitogen bilan faollashtirilgan protein, NF-a.B, NF-blok, NF-blok kabi bir nechta hujayra maqsadlarini blok qilishni o'z ichiga oladi [83-85]. Uning GEB yaxlitligini himoya qilish NADga bog'liq deatsetilaz sirtuin-3 (SIRT-3)/prolil gidroksilaza domenini o'z ichiga olgan protein 2 (PHD-2) orqali gipoksiyani qo'zg'atuvchi omil 1-alfa yo`li (HIF-1a) hujayra reaksiyalarini bloklash orqali sodir bo'ladi [86]. Biroq, BMJga qarshi mumkin bo'lgan terapevtik foydalanish uchun qo'shimcha klinik tadqiqotlar hali ham talab qilinadi.

4. Oksidlanish stress. YBMJdagi oksidlovchi stress reaktiv kislorod turlari va boshqa erkin radikallar ishlab chiqarishning ko'payishi sifatida ifodalanadi. Bu jarayonda asosiy rol ni fosfolipaza A2 va araxidon kislotasi bajaradi. Ishemiya paytida glutamatning chiqarilishi va hujayra ichidagi Ca^{2+} ning ko'payishi sitozoldagi Ca^{2+} ga bog'liq PLA2ni faollashtiradi, bu fosfolipid gidroliziga va erkin yog'kislotalarining ajralishiga olib keladi [87, 88]. Boshqa tomondan, erkin araxidon kislotasining hujayra ichidagi to'planishi oksidlovchi zararni kuchaytiradigan reaktiv kislorod turlarining shakllanishiga yordam beradi [88]. Yakuniy natija to'g'ridan-to'g'ri neyron hujayralarining o'limi yoki mitoxondriyal disfunktsiyasi kuzatilib, glial hujayra faollashuvi, oqsilning noto'g'ri qatlamlanishi, gen ekspressiyasi, hujayra signalizatsiyasi va proteosomal anomaliyalar kabi boshqa hodisalardir oqibatida bo'ladi va ushbu mexanizmlarning ba'zilari apoptozga boshlaydi [89-92]. Oksidlanish stressdagi moddalar eksitotoksiklik, hujayra nafasini blok qilish va yallig'lanishning qo'shimcha mahsuloti ekanligi ko'rsatilgan [93]. Oksidlanish stressini neytrallashtirish ishemiyanini davolash uchun qiziqarli potentsial terapevtik variant bo'lsada, hayotiy birikmalarni topish juda qiyin bo'lib chiqdi.

4.1 Sitikolin. Sitikolin - sitidin difosfat xolin sifatida ham tanilgan, ikki molekula, sitidin va xolindan tashkil topgan birikma bo'lib, xolindan fosfatidilxolin hosil bo'lishida vositachi hisoblanadi. Eksperimental tadqiqotlarda u ko'p maqsadli va markaziy asab tizimining bir nechta kasalliklariga qarshi samarali ekanligi ko'rsatilgan [94-96]. Ikkala molekula ham qon-miya to'sig'idan o'ta oladi [97]. Qon tomirlarida sitikolin ko'p bosqichli ta'sirga ega bo'lgan uzoqroq vaqt oynasiga ega ekanligi ko'rsatilgan [98, 99]. Klinik tadqiqotlarda shunga o'xshash natijalar funksional natijalarning aniq yaxshilanishi bilan olingan. Sitikolinning antioksidant ta'siri fosfolipaza faollashishini oldini olish yoki susaytirish orqali amalga oshiriladi.

4.2. Edaravon. Edaravon - past molekulyar og'irlikdagi antioksidant bo'lib, reaktiv kislorod turlarining ko'p turlari orasida peroksil radikallarini aniq maqsad qilib oladi. Amfifilligi tufayli u lipidda ham, suvda ham eriydigan peroksil radikallarini o'zlashtiradi va elektronni radikalga o'tkazadi. Shunday qilib, zanjirli kimyoviy reaksiyalarni boshlaydigan suvda eriydigan peroksil radikallarini, shuningdek zanjirni saqlaydigan yog'da eriydigan peroksil radikallarini tozalash orqali lipid oksidlanishini ingibitsiya qiladi. Ishemik miya infarktining o'tkir bosqichida preparat himoya ta'sirini ko'rsatadi, miya shishi, nevrologik simptomlar va neyronlarning sekin o'limi kabi ishemiya serebrovaskulyar kasalliklarning paydo bo'lishi va rivojlanishini bostiradi [103].

5. Bir nechta maqsadli variantlar. Qon tomirlarini davolashning yangi terapevtik variantlarini izlashda ko'plab birikmalar ishemiya bilan qo'zg'atilgan patofiziologik o'zgarishlarga ko'p maqsadli va ko'p qirrali ta'sir ko'rsatadi; Ular orasida ikkita birikma, N-butilftalid (NBP) va inson siydik tizimidan kallidinogenaz allaqachon tasdiqlangan va Xitoyda klinik foydalanish uchun kiritilgan.

5.1 N-Butilftalid (NBP). Selderey yog'ining tarkibiy qismlaridan biri ajoyib ko'p yo'nalishtiruvchi neyroprotektiv xususiyatlarni namoyish etdi. U trombositlar agregatsiyasi ta'siri sababli antitrombotik ta'sirni ko'rsatadi, bu trombositlar siklik adenosin monofosfat (cAMP) darajasini oshirish va serotoninning chiqarilishini blok qilish orqali yuzaga keladi [102]. Keng ko'lamliligi tadqiqotlar, shuningdek, NBP Bcl-2 va HIF-1a darajalarini oshirish va kaspaza-3 ifodasini kamaytirish orqali antiapoptotik ta'sirga ega degan xulosaga keldi [103]. Bundan tashqari, u mitoxondriyadagi Na^{+}/K^{+} -ATFaz va Ca^{2+} -ATFazni yaxshilash va sitoxrom c chiqarilishini kamaytirish orqali mitoxondriyal shikastlanishga qarshi himoya xususiyatlarini ko'rsatadi [104]. Bundan tashqari, eksperimental modellarda NBP uzoq muddatli

administratsiyadan keyin antioksidant ta'sir ko'rsatdi. Asosiy mexanizm malondialdegid (MDA) darajasining oshishi [105] va vodorod peroksid (H_2O_2) ga bog'liq radikallarni to'planishining pasayishi [106]. Bularning barchasi iskemiya qarshi samarali ekanligini ko'rsatdi. Keng klinik sinovlardan so'ng, NBP allaqachon tasdiqlangan va qoniqarli natijalar bilan 12 yil davomida Xitoyda ishlatilgan.

5.2 Inson siydigi kallidinogenazasi. Kallidinogenaza - kallikrein/kinin tizimining (KKS) tarkibiy qismi bo'lgan kallikrein to'qimalarining ishemiyaga qarshi himoya ta'siri klinik va eksperimental tadqiqotlarda ko'rsatilgan. KKS regulyatori va kallikrein ishlab chiqaruvchisi bo'lgan inson siydik kallidinogenazasi yallig'lanishga qarshi, apoptotik, angiogen va neyrogenizatsiya faolligini namoyish etadi va Xitoyda insultni davolash uchun tasdiqlangan [107]. Bir qator tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatdiki, kallidinogenazasi funktsional kamchiliklarni yaxshilaydi [108, 109], angiogenezni rag'batlantiradi va miya qon oqimini yaxshilaydi [110]. Asosiy mexanizm qon tomir endotelial o'sish omili va apelin/APJ yo'lining ko'tarilishi va bradikinin B1 va B2 retseptorlari faollashuvidir [111, 112]. Bundan tashqari, kallidinogenazasi kognitiv samaradorlikni yaxshilashi va plazmada Ab1-40 va Ab1-42 darajalarini kamaytirishi ko'rsatilgan [113]. Bundan tashqari, to'qimalarni kallikreinni oldindan davolash neyronal azot oksidi sintaza faolligini ingibitsiya qilish va hujayradan tashqari signal bilan boshqariladigan kinaz 1 (ERK1) va NF-kB faollashuvi orqali glutamatdan kelib chiqqan oksidlovchi stressni kamaytirishi ko'rsatilgan, natijada miyadan kelib chiqqan neyrotrofik omilning mRNK va antiapoptotik gen Bcl-2 oqsilining ko'payishiga olib keladi [114].

XULOSA

YBMJni davolashning yangi terapevtik usullarini izlash har doim qiziqarli bo'lib kelgan. Biroq patologiyaning murakkabligi tufayli yangi neyroprotektiv preparatlarni ishlab chiqish yanada qiyin vazifa ekanligini isbotladi. Bir tomondan, muvaffaqiyatsiz klinik izlanishlar sonining tobora ortib borayotgani YBMJning murakkabligini va yaxshiroq nazorat qilinadigan sinovlarga ehtiyoj borligini ta'kidlaydi. Boshqa tomondan, YBMJdan keyingi ko'plab patofiziologik faoliyatlarning ikki tomonlama ta'siri konsentratsiyasi, vaqti, joyi va yuzaga kelgan sharoitlariga qarab foydali yoki zararli bo'lishi mumkin. Biroq, klinik foydalanishga muvaffaqiyatli kiritilgan bir nechta birikmalar bilan ijobiy natijalar ko'rsatdiki, yangi samarali neyroprotektiv variantlarni kashf qilish jarayoni uzoq va iqtisodiy qimmat bo'lsa ham, neyroproteksiya hali ham hayotiy va kelajak uchun eng yaxshi davolash usullaridan biri hisoblanadi.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

1. Avakov V.E., Ibragimov N.K., Murotov TM.N., Kenjaev L.T. Comparative characteristics of the effects of hyperosmolar therapy in patients with craniocerebral trauma. Вестник Ташкентской медицинской академии 2018 № 3 97-101 с.
2. Gaytur E.I., Potapov A.A. et al. The influence of arterial hypotension on the course and outcomes of severe traumatic brain injury // Resuscitation at the turn of the 21st century. – M., 2006. – 126 p.
3. Kahle K.T., Simard J.M. et al. Molecular mechanisms of ischemic cerebral edema: Role of electroneutral ion transport // Physiology (Bethesda). – 2009. – Vol. 24. – P. 257-265.
4. Kamel H., Navi B.B. et al. Hypertonic saline versus mannitol for the treatment of elevated intracranial pressure: a metaanalysis of randomized clinical trials // Crit. Care Med. – 2011. Vol. 39. – P. 554-559
5. Kaufmann A.M., Cardoso E.R. Aggravation of vasogenic cerebral edema by multiple-dose mannitol // J. Neurosurg. – 1992. – Vol. 77. – P. 584-589.

6. Kerwin A.J., Schinco M.A. et al. The use of 23.4% hypertonic saline for the management of elevated intracranial pressure in patients with severe traumatic brain injury: a pilot study // *J. Trauma*. – 2009. – Vol. 67. – P. 277-282.
7. Zadori D, Klivenyi P, Szalardy L, Fulop F, Toldi J, Vecsei L. Mitochondrial Disturbances, Excitotoxicity, Neuroinflammation and Kynurenines: Novel Therapeutic Strategies for Neurodegenerative Disorders. *J Neurol Sci*. 2012;322:187-91.
8. Majid A. Neuroprotection in Stroke: Past, Present, and Future. *ISRN Neurol*. 2014;2014:515716.
9. Krylov V.V. Surgery of severe traumatic brain injury. Under the general editorship of Krylova V.V. Moscow, 2019. 647 p.
10. Donnan GA, Davis SM, Parsons MW, Ma H, Dewey HM, Howells DW. How to Make Better Use of Thrombolytic Therapy in Acute Ischemic Stroke. *Nat Rev Neurol*. 2011;7:400-9.
11. Shuaib A, Hussain MS. The Past and Future of Neuroprotection in Cerebral Ischaemic Stroke. *Eur Neurol*. 2008;59:4-14.
12. Fisher M. New Approaches to Neuroprotective Drug Development. *Stroke*. 2011;42:S24-7.
13. Wahlgren NG, Ahmed N. Neuroprotection in Cerebral Ischaemia: Facts and Fancies--the Need for New Approaches. *Cerebrovasc Dis*. 2004;17 Suppl 1:153-66.
14. Deb P, Sharma S, Hassan KM. Pathophysiologic Mechanisms of Acute Ischemic Stroke: An Overview with Emphasis on Therapeutic Significance Beyond Thrombolysis. *Pathophysiology*. 2010;17:197-218.
15. Jablonska A, Lukomska B. Stroke Induced Brain Changes: Implications for Stem Cell Transplantation. *Acta Neurobiol Exp (Wars)*. 2011;71:74-85.
16. Yang DD, Kuan CY, Whitmarsh AJ, Rincon M, Zheng TS, Davis RJ, et al. Absence of Excitotoxicity-Induced Apoptosis in the Hippocampus of Mice Lacking the *Jnk3* Gene. *Nature*. 1997;389:865-70.
17. Ankarcona M, Dypbukt JM, Bonfoco E, Zhivotovsky B, Orrenius S, Lipton SA, et al. Glutamate-Induced Neuronal Death: A Succession of Necrosis or Apoptosis Depending on Mitochondrial Function. *Neuron*. 1995;15:961-73.
18. Dutta R, Trapp BD. Mechanisms of Neuronal Dysfunction and Degeneration in Multiple Sclerosis. *Prog Neurobiol*. 2011;93:1-12.
19. Jaiswal MK, Zech WD, Goos M, Leutbecher C, Ferri A, Zippelius A, et al. Impairment of Mitochondrial Calcium Handling in *Mtsod1* Cell Culture Model of Motoneuron Disease. *BMC Neurosci*. 2009;10:64.
20. Manev H, Favaron M, Guidotti A, Costa E. Delayed Increase of Ca²⁺ Influx Elicited by Glutamate: Role in Neuronal Death. *Mol Pharmacol*. 1989;36:106-12.
21. Kaur H, Prakash A, Medhi B. Drug Therapy in Stroke: From Preclinical to Clinical Studies. *Pharmacology*. 2013;92:324-34.
22. White BC, Sullivan JM, DeGracia DJ, O'Neil BJ, Neumar RW, Grossman LI, et al. Brain Ischemia and Reperfusion: Molecular Mechanisms of Neuronal Injury. *J Neurol Sci*. 2000;179:1-33.
23. Stavrovskaya IG, Kristal BS. The Powerhouse Takes Control of the Cell: Is the Mitochondrial Permeability Transition a Viable Therapeutic Target against Neuronal Dysfunction and Death? *Free Radic Biol Med*. 2005;38:687-97.
24. Kristian T, Siesjo BK. Calcium-Related Damage in Ischemia. *Life Sci*. 1996;59:357-67.
25. Zhang J, Yang J, Zhang C, Jiang X, Zhou H, Liu M. Calcium Antagonists for Acute Ischemic Stroke. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev*. 2012:CD001928.
26. Nowak L, Bregestovski P, Ascher P, Herbet A, Prochiantz A. Magnesium Gates Glutamate-Activated Channels in Mouse Central Neurons. *Nature*. 1984;307:462-5.
27. Izumi Y, Roussel S, Pinard E, Seylaz J. Reduction of Infarct Volume by Magnesium after Middle Cerebral Artery Occlusion in Rats. *J Cereb Blood Flow Metab*. 1991;11:1025-30.

28. Muir KW, Lees KR, Ford I, Davis S, Intravenous Magnesium Efficacy in Stroke Study I. Magnesium for Acute Stroke (Intravenous Magnesium Efficacy in Stroke Trial): Randomised Controlled Trial. *Lancet*. 2004;363:439-45.
29. Saver JL, Kidwell C, Eckstein M, Starkman S, Investigators FMPT. Prehospital Neuroprotective Therapy for Acute Stroke: Results of the Field Administration of Stroke Therapy-Magnesium (Fast-Mag) Pilot Trial. *Stroke*. 2004;35:e106-8.
30. Grupke S, Hall J, Dobbs M, Bix GJ, Fraser JF. Understanding History, and Not Repeating It. Neuroprotection for Acute Ischemic Stroke: From Review to Preview. *Clin Neurol Neurosurg*. 2015;129:1-9.
31. Lehmann J, Hutchison AJ, McPherson SE, Mondadori C, Schmutz M, et al. Cgs 19755, a Selective and Competitive N-Methyl-D-Aspartate-Type Excitatory Amino Acid Receptor Antagonist. *J Pharmacol Exp Ther*. 1988;246:6575.
32. Miyabe M, Kirsch JR, Nishikawa T, Koehler RC, Traystman RJ. Comparative Analysis of Brain Protection by N-Methyl-D-Aspartate Receptor Antagonists after Transient Focal Ischemia in Cats. *Crit Care Med*. 1997;25:1037-43.
33. Simon R, Shiraishi K. N-Methyl-D-Aspartate Antagonist Reduces Stroke Size and Regional Glucose Metabolism. *Ann Neurol*. 1990;27:606-11.
34. Grotta J, Clark W, Coull B, Pettigrew LC, Mackay B, Goldstein LB, et al. Safety and Tolerability of the Glutamate Antagonist Cgs 19755 (Selfotel) in Patients with Acute Ischemic Stroke. Results of a Phase Iia Randomized Trial. *Stroke*. 1995;26:602-5.
35. Davis SM, Lees KR, Albers GW, Diener HC, Markabi S, Karlsson G, et al. Selfotel in Acute Ischemic Stroke : Possible Neurotoxic Effects of an Nmda Antagonist. *Stroke*. 2000;31:347-54.
36. Jain KK. *The Handbook of Neuroprotection*. 1. ed. Totowa, NJ: Springer Science+Business Media, LLC; 2011.
37. Suzuki M, Sasamata M, Miyata K. Neuroprotective Effects of Ym872 Coadministered with T-Pa in a Rat Embolic Stroke Model. *Brain Res*. 2003;959:169-72.
38. Furukawa T, Hoshino S, Kobayashi S, Asakura T, Takahashi M, Atsumi T, et al. The Glutamate Ampa Receptor Antagonist, Ym872, Attenuates Cortical Tissue Loss, Regional Cerebral Edema, and Neurological Motor Deficits after Experimental Brain Injury in Rats. *J Neurotrauma*. 2003;20:269-78.
39. Farooqui AA. *Neurochemical Aspects of Neurotraumatic and Neurodegenerative Diseases*. New York, NY: Springer Science+Business Media, LLC; 2010.
40. Garcia JH, Yoshida Y, Chen H, Li Y, Zhang ZG, Lian J, et al. Progression from Ischemic Injury to Infarct Following Middle Cerebral Artery Occlusion in the Rat. *Am J Pathol*. 1993;142:623-35.
41. Broughton BR, Reutens DC, Sobey CG. Apoptotic Mechanisms after Cerebral Ischemia. *Stroke*. 2009;40:e331-9.
42. Li Y, Chopp M, Jiang N, Yao F, Zaloga C. Temporal Profile of in Situ DNA Fragmentation after Transient Middle Cerebral Artery Occlusion in the Rat. *J Cereb Blood Flow Metab*. 1995;15:389-97.
43. Li Y, Chopp M, Jiang N, Zhang ZG, Zaloga C. Induction of DNA Fragmentation after 10 to 120 Minutes of Focal Cerebral Ischemia in Rats. *Stroke*. 1995;26:1252-7; discussion 7-8.
44. Mattson MP, Culmsee C, Yu ZF. Apoptotic and Antiapoptotic Mechanisms in Stroke. *Cell Tissue Res*. 2000;301:173-87.
45. MacManus JP, Buchan AM. Apoptosis after Experimental Stroke: Fact or Fashion? *J Neurotrauma*. 2000;17:899-914.
46. Elliott S, Sinclair AM. The Effect of Erythropoietin on Normal and Neoplastic Cells. *Biologics*. 2012;6:163-89.
47. Chong ZZ, Kang JQ, Maiese K. Erythropoietin Is a Novel Vascular Protectant through Activation of Akt1 and Mitochondrial Modulation of Cysteine Proteases. *Circulation*. 2002;106:2973-9.

48. Digicaylioglu M. Erythropoietin in Stroke: Quo Vadis. *Expert Opin Biol Ther.* 2010;10:937-49.
49. Wen TC, Sadamoto Y, Tanaka J, Zhu PX, Nakata K, Ma YJ, et al. Erythropoietin Protects Neurons against Chemical Hypoxia and Cerebral Ischemic Injury by up-Regulating Bcl-Xl Expression. *J Neurosci Res.* 2002;67:795-803.
50. Ehrenreich H, Hasselblatt M, Dembowski C, Cepek L, Lewczuk P, Stiefel M, et al. Erythropoietin Therapy for Acute Stroke Is Both Safe and Beneficial. *Mol Med.*2002;8:495-505.
51. Ehrenreich H, Weissenborn K, Prange H, Schneider D, Weimar C, Wartenberg K, et al. Recombinant Human Erythropoietin in the Treatment of Acute Ischemic Stroke. *Stroke.* 2009;40:e647-56.
52. Heiss WD, Brainin M, Bornstein NM, Tuomilehto J, Hong Z, Cerebrolysin Acute Stroke Treatment in Asia I. Cerebrolysin in Patients with Acute Ischemic Stroke in Asia: Results of a DoubleBlind, Placebo-Controlled Randomized Trial. *Stroke.* 2012;43:630-6.
53. Menon PK, Muresanu DF, Sharma A, Mossler H, Sharma HS. Cerebrolysin, a Mixture of Neurotrophic Factors Induces Marked Neuroprotection in Spinal Cord Injury Following Intoxication of Engineered Nanoparticles from Metals. *CNS Neurol Disord Drug Targets.* 2012;11:40-9.
54. Hartbauer M, Hutter-Paier B, Skofitsch G, Windisch M. Antiapoptotic Effects of the Peptidergic Drug Cerebrolysin on Primary Cultures of Embryonic Chick Cortical Neurons. *J Neural Transm (Vienna).* 2001;108:459-73.
55. Zhang L, Chopp M, Meier DH, Winter S, Wang L, Szalad A, et al. Sonic Hedgehog Signaling Pathway Mediates CerebrolysinImproved Neurological Function after Stroke. *Stroke.* 2013;44:1965-
56. Gutmann B, Hutter-Paier B, Skofitsch G, Windisch M, Gmeinbauer R. In Vitro Models of Brain Ischemia: The Peptidergic Drug Cerebrolysin Protects Cultured Chick Cortical Neurons from Cell Death. *Neurotox Res.*2002;4:59-65.
57. Masliah E, Diez-Tejedor E. The Pharmacology of Neurotrophic Treatment with Cerebrolysin: Brain Protection and Repair to Counteract Pathologies of Acute and Chronic Neurological Disorders. *Drugs Today (Barc).* 2012;48 Suppl A:3-24.
58. Muresanu DF, Heiss WD, Hoemberg V, Bajenaru O, Popescu CD, Vester JC, et al. Cerebrolysin and Recovery after Stroke (Cars): A Randomized, Placebo-Controlled, Double-Blind, Multicenter Trial. *Stroke.* 2016;47:151-9.
59. Zhang C, Chopp M, Cui Y, Wang L, Zhang R, Zhang L, et al. Cerebrolysin Enhances Neurogenesis in the Ischemic Brain and Improves Functional Outcome after Stroke. *J Neurosci Res.* 2010;88:3275-81.
60. Amiri-Nikpour MR, Nazarbaghi S, Ahmadi-Salmasi B, Mokari T, Tahamtan U, Rezaei Y. Cerebrolysin Effects on Neurological Outcomes and Cerebral Blood Flow in Acute Ischemic Stroke. *Neuropsychiatr Dis Treat.* 2014;10:2299-306.
61. Chamorro A, Hallenbeck J. The Harms and Benefits of Inflammatory and Immune Responses in Vascular Disease. *Stroke.* 2006;37:291-3.
62. Barone FC, Feuerstein GZ. Inflammatory Mediators and Stroke: New Opportunities for Novel Therapeutics. *J Cereb Blood Flow Metab.*1999;19:819-34.
63. Becker KJ. Inflammation and Acute Stroke. *Curr Opin Neurol.* 1998;11:45-9
64. Stanimirovic DB, Wong J, Shapiro A, Durkin JP. Increase in Surface Expression of Icam-1, Vcam-1 and E-Selectin in Human Cerebromicrovascular Endothelial Cells Subjected to Ischemia-Like Insults. *Acta Neurochir Suppl.* 1997;70:12-6.
65. Danton GH, Dietrich WD. Inflammatory Mechanisms after Ischemia and Stroke. *J Neuropathol Exp Neurol.* 2003;62:127-36.
66. Basu A, Lazovic J, Krady JK, Mauger DT, Rothstein RP, Smith MB, et al. Interleukin-1 and the Interleukin-1 Type 1 Receptor Are Essential for the Progressive Neurodegeneration That Ensues Subsequent to a Mild Hypoxic/Ischemic Injury. *J Cereb Blood Flow Metab.* 2005;25:17-29.

67. Peberdy MA, Callaway CW, Neumar RW, Geocadin RG, Zimmerman JL, Donnino M, et al. Part 9: Post-Cardiac Arrest Care: 2010 American Heart Association Guidelines for Cardiopulmonary Resuscitation and Emergency Cardiovascular Care. *Circulation*. 2010;122:S768-86.
68. Polderman KH. Application of Therapeutic Hypothermia in the Icu: Opportunities and Pitfalls of a Promising Treatment Modality. Part 1: Indications and Evidence. *Intensive Care Med*. 2004;30:556-75.
69. Milde LN. Clinical Use of Mild Hypothermia for Brain Protection: A Dream Revisited. *J Neurosurg Anesthesiol*. 1992;4:211-5.
70. Ehrlich MP, McCullough JN, Zhang N, Weisz DJ, Juvonen T, Bodian CA, et al. Effect of Hypothermia on Cerebral Blood Flow and Metabolism in the Pig. *Ann Thorac Surg*. 2002;73:191-7.
71. Erecinska M, Thoresen M, Silver IA. Effects of Hypothermia on Energy Metabolism in Mammalian Central Nervous System. *J Cereb Blood Flow Metab*. 2003;23:513-30.
72. Polderman KH. Mechanisms of Action, Physiological Effects, and Complications of Hypothermia. *Crit Care Med*. 2009;37:S186-202.
73. Busto R, Dietrich WD, Globus MY, Ginsberg MD. Postischemic Moderate Hypothermia Inhibits Ca1 Hippocampal Ischemic Neuronal Injury. *Neurosci Lett*. 1989;101:299-304.
74. Baldwin WA, Kirsch JR, Hurn PD, Toung WS. Hypothermic Cerebral Reperfusion and Recovery from Ischemia. *Am J Physiol*. 1991;261:H774 81.
75. Wang GJ, Deng HY, Maier CM, Sun GH, Yenari MA. Mild Hypothermia Reduces Icam-1 Expression, Neutrophil Infiltration and Microglia/Monocyte Accumulation Following Experimental Stroke. *Neuroscience*. 2002;114:1081-90.
76. Perrone S, Szabo M, Bellieni CV, Longini M, Bango M, Kelen D, et al. Whole Body Hypothermia and Oxidative Stress in Babies with Hypoxic-Ischemic Brain Injury. *Pediatr Neurol*. 2010;43:236-40.
77. Meybohm P, Gruenewald M, Zacharowski KD, Albrecht M, Lucius R, Foesel N, et al. Mild Hypothermia Alone or in Combination with Anesthetic Post-Conditioning Reduces Expression of Inflammatory Cytokines in the Cerebral Cortex of Pigs after Cardiopulmonary Resuscitation. *Crit Care*. 2010;14:R21.
78. Choi JS, Park J, Suk K, Moon C, Park YK, Han HS. Mild Hypothermia Attenuates Intercellular Adhesion Molecule-1 Induction Via Activation of Extracellular Signal-Regulated Kinase-1/2 in a Focal Cerebral Ischemia Model. *Stroke Res Treat*. 2011;2011:846716.
79. Maier K, Merkler D, Gerber J, Taheri N, Kuhnert AV, Williams SK, et al. Multiple Neuroprotective Mechanisms of Minocycline in Autoimmune Cns Inflammation. *Neurobiol Dis*. 2007;25:514-25.
80. Tikka TM, Vartiainen NE, Goldsteins G, Oja SS, Andersen PM, Marklund SL, et al. Minocycline Prevents Neurotoxicity Induced by Cerebrospinal Fluid from Patients with Motor Neurone Disease. *Brain*. 2002;125:722-31.
81. Tikka TM, Koistinaho JE. Minocycline Provides Neuroprotection against N-Methyl-D-Aspartate Neurotoxicity by Inhibiting Microglia. *J Immunol*. 2001;166:7527-33.
82. Brundula V, Rewcastle NB, Metz LM, Bernard CC, Yong VW. Targeting Leukocyte Mmps and Transmigration: Minocycline as a Potential Therapy for Multiple Sclerosis. *Brain*. 2002;125:1297-308.
83. Wang X, Zhu S, Drozda M, Zhang W, Stavrovskaya IG, Cattaneo E, et al. Minocycline Inhibits Caspase-Independent and -Dependent Mitochondrial Cell Death Pathways in Models of Huntington's Disease. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A*. 2003;100:10483-7.
84. Chen M, Ona VO, Li M, Ferrante RJ, Fink KB, Zhu S, et al. Minocycline Inhibits Caspase-1 and Caspase-3 Expression and Delays Mortality in a Transgenic Mouse Model of Huntington Disease. *Nat Med*. 2000;6:797-801.

85. Yrjanheikki J, Tikka T, Keinanen R, Goldsteins G, Chan PH, Koistinaho J. A Tetracycline Derivative, Minocycline, Reduces Inflammation and Protects against Focal Cerebral Ischemia with a Wide Therapeutic Window. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U SA*.1999;96:13496-500.
86. Yang F, Zhou L, Wang D, Wang Z, Huang QY. Minocycline Ameliorates Hypoxia-Induced Blood–Brain Barrier Damage by Inhibition of Hif-1 α through Sirt-3/Phd-2 Degradation Pathway. *Neuroscience*. 2015;304:250-9.
87. Kim DK, Rordorf G, Nemenoff RA, Koroshetz WJ, Bonventre JV. Glutamate Stably Enhances the Activity of Two Cytosolic Forms of Phospholipase A2 in Brain Cortical Cultures. *Biochem J*. 1995;310 (Pt1):83-90.
88. Katsuki H, Okuda S. Arachidonic Acid as a Neurotoxic and Neurotrophic Substance. *Prog Neurobiol*.1995;46:607-36.
89. Seidl SE, Potashkin JA. The Promise of Neuroprotective Agents in Parkinson's Disease. *Front Neurol*. 2011;2:68.
90. Dunnett SB, Bjorklund A. Prospects for New Restorative and Neuroprotective Treatments in Parkinson's Disease. *Nature*. 1999;399:A32-9.
91. Chan PH. Reactive Oxygen Radicals in Signaling and Damage in the Ischemic Brain. *J Cereb Blood Flow Metab*. 2001;21:2-14.
92. Liu T, Bitan G. Modulating Self-Assembly of Amyloidogenic Proteins as a Therapeutic Approach for Neurodegenerative Diseases: Strategies and Mechanisms. *ChemMedChem*. 2012;7:359-74.
93. Pradeep H, Diya JB, Shashikumar S, Rajanikant GK. Oxidative Stress--Assassin Behind the Ischemic Stroke. *Folia Neuropathol*. 2012;50:219-30.
94. Secades JJ, Alvarez-Sabin J, Rubio F, Lozano R, Davalos A, Castillo J, et al. Citicoline in Intracerebral Haemorrhage: A DoubleBlind, Randomized, Placebo Controlled, Multi-Centre Pilot Study. *Cerebrovasc Dis*. 2006;21:380-5.
95. Cho HJ, Kim YJ. Efficacy and Safety of Oral Citicoline in Acute Ischemic Stroke: Drug Surveillance Study in 4,191 Cases. *Methods Find Exp Clin Pharmacol*. 2009;31:171-6.
96. Alvarez-Sabin J, Ortega G, Jacas C, Santamarina E, Maisterra O, Ribo M, et al. Long-Term Treatment with Citicoline May Improve Poststroke Vascular Cognitive Impairment. *Cerebrovasc Dis*. 2013;35:146-54.
97. IL GC, Wurtman RJ. Enhancement by Cytidine of Membrane Phospholipid Synthesis. *J Neurochem*. 1992;59:338-43.
98. Schabitz WR, Weber J, Takano K, Sandage BW, Locke KW, Fisher M. The Effects of Prolonged Treatment with Citicoline in Temporary Experimental Focal Ischemia. *J Neurol Sci*. 1996;138:21-5.
99. Hurtado O, Pradillo JM, Fernandez-Lopez D, Morales JR, Sobrino T, Castillo J, et al. Delayed Post-Ischemic Administration of Cdp-Choline Increases Eaat2 Association to Lipid Rafts and Affords Neuroprotection in Exp Stroke. *Neurobiol Dis*. 2008;29:123-31.
100. Adibhatla RM, Hatcher JF, Dempsey RJ. Citicoline: Neuroprotective Mechanisms in Cerebral Ischemia. *J Neurochem*. 2002;80:12-23.
101. Rao AM, Hatcher JF, Dempsey RJ. Cdp-Choline: Neuroprotection in Transient Forebrain Ischemia of Gerbils. *J Neurosci Res*. 1999;58:697-705.
102. De La Cruz JP, Villalobos MA, Cuerda MA, Guerrero A, Gonzalez-Correa JA, Sanchez De La Cuesta F. Effects of S-Adenosyl-L-Methionine on Lipid Peroxidation and Glutathione Levels in Rat Brain Slices Exposed to Reoxygenation after Oxygen-Glucose Deprivation. *Neurosci Lett*. 2002;318:103-7.
103. Ramazanov Z.F., Avakov V.E., Ibragimov N.K., Muralimova R.S., Boymurodov H. Efficiency of complex neuroprotection with the use of the drug Edaravone (Radixoba-Tsommer) Tashkent Medical Academy Department of Anesthesiology and Resuscitation.
104. He WF, Zhou WS, Hu ZP. Chinese Herbal Extract DI-3nButylphthalide a Commonly Used Drug for the Treatment of Ischemic Stroke as a Novel Therapeutic Approach to Treat Neurodegenerative

- Diseases. *Neural Regeneration Research*. 2011;6:2773-8.
105. Zhao W, Luo C, Wang J, Gong J, Li B, Gong Y, et al. 3-N-Butylphthalide Improves Neuronal Morphology after Chronic Cerebral Ischemia. *Neural Regen Res*. 2014;9:719-26.
 106. Sun B, Feng MJ, Tian XY, Lu XW, Zhang YY, Ke XJ, et al. DL- 3-N-Butylphthalide Protects Rat Bone Marrow Stem Cells against Hydrogen Peroxide-Induced Cell Death through Antioxidation and Activation of Pi3k-Akt Pathway. *Neuroscience Letters*. 2012;516:247-52.
 107. Chao J, Chao L. Experimental Therapy with Tissue Kallikrein against Cerebral Ischemia. *Front Biosci*. 2006;11:1323-7.
 108. Zhang C, Tao W, Liu M, Wang D. Efficacy and Safety of Human Urinary Kallidinogenase Injection for Acute Ischemic Stroke: A Systematic Review. *J Evid Based Med*. 2012;5:31-9.
 109. Li C, Zha OG, He QY, Wu YZ, Wang TS, Teng JF. Study on the Clinical Efficacy of Human Urinary Kallikrein in the Treatment of Acute Cerebral Infarction According to Toast Classification. *Pak J Pharm Sci*. 2015;28:1505-10.
 110. Miao J, Deng F, Zhang Y, Xie HY, Feng JC. Exogenous Human Urinary Kallidinogenase Increases Cerebral Blood Flow in Patients with Acute Ischemic Stroke. *Neurosci (Riyadh)*. 2016;21:126-30.
 111. Li J, Chen Y, Zhang X, Zhang B, Zhang M, Xu Y. Human Urinary Kallidinogenase Improves Outcome of Stroke Patients by Shortening Mean Transit Time of Perfusion Magnetic Resonance Imaging. *J Stroke Cerebrovasc Dis*. 2015;24:1730-7.
 112. Han L, Li J, Chen Y, Zhang M, Qian L, Chen Y, et al. Human Urinary Kallidinogenase Promotes Angiogenesis and Cerebral Perfusion in Experimental Stroke. *PLoS One*. 2015;10:e0134543.
 113. Zhao L, Zhao Y, Wan Q, Zhang H. Urinary Kallidinogenase for the Treatment of Cerebral Arterial Stenosis. *Drug Des Devel Ther*. 2015;9:5595-600.
 114. Liu L, Zhang R, Liu K, Zhou H, Tang Y, Su J, et al. Tissue Kallikrein Alleviates Glutamate-Induced Neurotoxicity by Activating Erk1. *Journal of Neuroscience Research*. 2009;87:3576-90.